

Netherlands Food and Consumer
Product Safety Authority
*Ministry of Agriculture,
Nature and Food Quality*

**Netherlands Food and
Consumer Product Safety
Authority (NVWA)**
-
**Office for Risk Assessment
and Research (BuRO)**

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Welcome

- NVWA is part of the central government, within LNV
- assignments by and budget from two ministries (LNV, VWS)
- laboratories (food safety; product safety; plant health)

Mission and role

The NVWA safeguards food safety, consumer product safety, animal health, animal welfare, plant health and maintains the legislation in the field of nature

Main tasks:

- risk assessment and communication
- verification: inspections, audits
- enforcement

NVWA – key facts and figures in 2016

- Budget: € 333 million
- 2471 total number staff
- number of controls: 160,455
- samples: \pm 510,000
- warnings, fines, etc.: \pm 22,000

More facts and figures available on our website:

<https://www.nvwa.nl/onderwerpen/toezicht-nvwa-eten-en-drinken/dossier/meerjarenprogramma-nationale-controles-mancp/jaarverslagen-mancp>

Approach of inspection and enforcement

The supply chain comprises many links, all vulnerable to introduction of risks.

Therefore we need to:

- assess those risks throughout the chain
- prioritise those risks to act most efficient
- work together to be most effective
- discover criminal hazardous activities

Knowledge-based and risk-oriented!

EFSA mission (EC/178/2000):

- Scientific advice concerning food safety;
- Communication on risks.

NVWA responsibilities:

- Identical, but includes law enforcement;
- Liaison office.

***Office for Risk Assessment &
Research***

Distinct tasks of risk assessment (BuRO) and risk management (NVWA) requires functional separation:

- To ensure that scientific assessment is independent and not influenced by other interests
- To demarcate that the acceptability of a risk is a matter for decision-makers, not risk assessors
- To ascertain that different issues are assessed by scientists with relevant competence

- Law on the Independent Risk Assessment VWA (*Wet Onafhankelijke Risicobeoordeling NVWA [WOR]*), April 26 2006, nr 247, is focussed on public health
 - › Food Safety
 - › Product Safety
 - › Intention as of 2014: include Animal Welfare in WOR
 - BuRO-employee ≠ enforcer, inspector!
 - Risk Assessment
 - › Hazard Identification
 - › Hazard Characterization (dose/response)
 - › Exposure Assessment
 - › Risk Characterization
- Advice, with action perspective & risk communication

EFSA

- EFSA should be a depository for the best expertise available
- Harmonisation of risk assessment methodology, generic assessment, EU food consumption/occurrence data bases, communication and ICT structure, EREN network, midterm planning

BuRO

- Advisory Forum member
- EFSA Focal Point
- Panels
- Networks

- (Short) Advices
 - › Varying from emails (minutes), written contributions (hours to days), to public advices (weeks to years)
 - › Generally, publicly available
- Contributions to 'the State of' (Product Safety, Food Safety)
- Risk Communication
- Risk Assessment of Supply (or Production) Chains

New and emerging risks

Early warnings - networks

- National (e.g., on zoonoses, chemical risks)
 - EFSA (Advisory Forum, Focal Point, EREN)
- Too many signals, weighing needed using risk matrix!

Active enforcement	Incidents and crisis control
Regular enforcement	Risk communication

Axes can comprise various parameters!

National Institute for Public Health
and the Environment
Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport

Risk assessment of TiO_2 nanoparticles in food, incl. toxicokinetic considerations

Minne Heringa et al.

NVWA workshop TiO_2 | 4-5 July 2018

Three papers:

- Intake
- Risk assessment
 - Based on modelled organ levels
 - Based on measured organ levels in humans

Then current work

Nanotoxicology

ISSN: 1743-5390 (Print) 1743-5404 (Online) Journal homepage: <http://www.tandfonline.com/loi/inan20>

Risk assessment of titanium dioxide nanoparticles via oral exposure, including toxicokinetic considerations

Minne B. Heringa, Liesbeth Geraets, Jan C. H. van Eijkeren, Rob J. Vandebriel, Wim H. de Jong & Agnes G. Oomen

Nanotoxicology

ISSN: 1743-5390 (Print) 1743-5404 (Online) Journal homepage: <http://www.tandfonline.com/loi/inan20>

Oral intake of added titanium dioxide and its nanofraction from food products, food supplements and toothpaste by the Dutch population

Cathy Rompelberg, Minne B. Heringa, Gerda van Donkersgoed, José Drijvers, Agnes Roos, Susanne Westenbrink, Ruud Peters, Greet van Bommel, Walter Brand & Agnes G. Oomen

Heringa et al. *Particle and Fibre Toxicology* (2018) 15:15
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12989-018-0251-7>

Particle and Fibre Toxicology

RESEARCH

Open Access

Detection of titanium particles in human liver and spleen and possible health implications

M. B. Heringa^{1*}, R. J. B. Peters², R. L. A. W. Bleys³, M. K. van der Lee², P. C. Tromp⁴, P. C. E. van Kesteren¹, J. C. H. van Eijkeren¹, A. K. Undas², A. G. Oomen¹ and H. Bouwmeester^{2,5}

Intake: method

- Aim: realistic estimation of oral intake of added titanium dioxide (TiO_2) and its nanofraction (nTiO_2) from food products, food supplements and toothpaste by the Dutch population (Rompelberg et al., 2016)
- TiO_2 levels from literature and analyses RIKILT
- Food product intake from Dutch National Food Consumption Survey, 3 age groups

- To calculate the nTiO_2 fraction (<100 nm) ingested, used a fraction of 0.31% (by mass, corresponding to 15% by number) of nano-sized particles calculated from the data of Peters et al. (2014)

Intake: main findings amount

Age groups	TiO ₂		Mean* (mg/kg bw per day)	TiO ₂ nanoparticles (TiO ₂ NPs)		Mean* (µg/kg bw per day)
	Percentiles of intake* (mg/kg bw per day)			Percentiles of intake* (µg/kg bw per day)		
	P50	P95		P50	P95	
2-6 y old	0.59 (0.57-0.60)	1.29 (1.19 – 1.40)	0.67 (0.66 - 0.70)	1.90 (1.80 – 1.94)	4.16 (3.84 – 4.52)	2.16 (2.13 – 2.26)
7-69 y old	0.08 (0.07 – 0.08)	0.50 (0.47 – 0.54)	0.17 (0.16 – 0.18)	0.26 (0.23 – 0.26)	1.61 (1.52 – 1.74)	0.55 (0.52 – 0.58)
70+	0.03 (0.02 – 0.03)	0.23 (0.20 – 0.28)	0.06 (0.05 – 0.07)	0.10 (0.06 – 0.10)	0.74 (0.65 – 0.90)	0.19 (0.16 – 0.23)
lifelong daily intake**	0.11	0.52	0.19	0.36	1.67	0.62

- P95: 95% of population has exposure at or below this level
- Natural sources not included, but have very low levels

Intake: main findings sources

Top ten	DNFCS-Children (2-6 y old)	DNFCS-2007-2010 (7-69 y old)	DNFCS-older adults (70+)
1	Toothpaste (57%)	Chewing gum (14%)	Coffee creamer (13%)
2	Hard candy with sugar (4%)	Coffee creamer (11%)	Thickened milk for coffee, powdered (8%)
3	Sugar-coated chocolate confectionery (3%)	Mayonnaise normal (7%)	Chewing gum (4%)
4	Chewing gum with sugar (2%)	Sauce, garlic, mayonnaise based (5%)	Cappuccino with cafein (3%)
5	Sugar-coated chocolates (2%)	Cappuccino (4%)	Cappuccino instant ready to drink (3%)
6	Biscuit with flavoured milk- filling (2%)	Thickened milk for coffee, powdered (3%)	Cappuccino (3%)
7	Biscuit with milk-filling (2%)	Iced cake 'glacekoek' (3%)	Sauce, garlic, mayonnaise based (2%)
8	Marsh mellow big (2%)	Cappuccino instant ready to drink (3%)	Pastries with cream (2%)
9	Biscuits with coffee glaze (2%)	Cappuccino with cafein (3%)	Sauce based on mayonnaise (2%)
10	Chewing gum sugar free (2%)	Coffee liquid with sugar and milk (machine) (2%)	Mayonnaise (2%)

Risk assessment: approach

- Approach 1: Margins between external exposure dose and external safe dose
- Approach 2: Margins between estimated/measured tissue concentrations in humans and the (no) effect concentrations in tissues obtained from toxicity studies in rodents (MoE_i).

E171 and nTiO₂ in risk assessment approach

- **Assumed that any toxicity is caused by the nanoparticles (<100 nm) present in E171.**
 - Artificial boundary
 - › In human tissue it was found that many of the TiO₂ particles were below or around 100 nm
- **Toxicity studies with E171 as well as with nTiO₂ used**
 - Exposure/dose was, if needed, converted to nanoparticles

Key toxicity studies

Study details	TiO ₂ details	Study-specific NOAEL or LOAEL (<i>self-derived levels in italics</i>)	Critical effects at LOAEL (not exhaustive)	Source
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 103 weeks • F344 rats, females and males • 50 animals/sex/dose • 0; 1250; 2500 mg/kg bw/day • Via diet 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anatase, uncoated, Unitane® 0-220 	NOAEL: 2500 mg/kg bw/d <i>LOAEL: 1250 mg/kg bw/d</i>	No significant carcinogenic effects or macroscopic lesions In annexes (without historic control range): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fibrosis in heart of male rats - Hyperplasia of bile ducts in male rats ↑, but no clear dose-response in female rat - (and more) 	NCI, 1979
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30 days • Sprague Dawley rats, males only • 7 animals/dose • 0; 10; 50; 200 mg/kg bw/day • Intragastric in water • Young rats (3 w) and adult rats (8 w) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anatase • 75 ± 15 nm average diameter • 63.95 m²/g (BET) • Hydroxyl groups on surface 	<i>Liver young: NOAEL: 10 mg/kg bw/day</i> <i>Liver adult: NOAEL: 50 mg/kg bw/d</i> <i>Spleen (young + adult): NOAEL: 200 mg/kg bw/day</i>	<u>Young rats:</u> Liver edema AST ↓ and ALT/AST ↑ (ALT unchanged) → liver damage HBDH ² ↓ → heart injury, but not dose-related Glucose and LDL-C ² ↑, but not dose-related <u>Adult rats:</u> TBIL ↑ → liver damage (multiple possible causes)	Wang et al., 2013

Key studies (continued)

Study details	TiO ₂ details	Study-specific NOAEL or LOAEL (<i>self-derived levels in italics</i>)	Critical effects at LOAEL (not exhaustive)	Source
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 42 days Kunming mice, males only • 15 animals/dose • 0; 10; 50; 250 mg/kg bw/day • Intragastric in PBS with 0.5 % Tween 80 • 4 weeks old at start of study 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anatase • 25 nm (indicated by supplier, no further details) 	<p><i>NOAEL: 10 mg/kg bw/d</i></p>	<p>Sperm abnormalities ↑ Testosterone levels in serum ↓ Vacuoles in seminiferous tubules</p>	Jia et al., 2014
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 days • Sprague Dawley rats, f + m • 7 animals/sex/dose • 0; 1; 2 mg/kg bw/day • Intragastric in water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anatase • Two different morphologies in tested material: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Spherical NPs with primary size 20-60 nm ○ Irregular NPs with primary size 40-60 nm 	<p><i>LOAEL: 1 mg/kg bw/day</i></p>	<p>Histopathological effects in thyroid, adrenal and ovary Testosterone in serum ♂ ↑ Testosterone in serum ♀ ↓ Triiodothyronine (T₃) in serum ♂ ↓ → thyroid system disrupted</p>	Tassinari et al., 2014

Toxicokinetics:

- Based on Geraets et al. (2014)
 - 4 TiO₂ materials, oral and IV, rat, 5 d exposure, 85 d post-exposure
 - 30% loss (dosing materials?)
 - Oral study: very low absorption: 0.02%
 - Highest levels in liver and spleen
 - Some elimination from liver, none from spleen → redistribution, accumulation
 - Hardly any total elimination

Estimated nTiO₂ concentrations in human organs

nTiO₂ concentration in different human organs plotted against age

Risk assessment: results

- Traditional approach: margins of safety (MoS) large enough, except for effects on repro-organs found by Tassinari et al.(2014)
- Approach incl. toxicokinetics: MoS too small, except for NCI study (1979)
 - Due to accumulation in organs in time

Conclusions:

- Risk cannot be excluded
- Important to include toxicokinetics as this changes risk assessment outcome for this accumulating substance

Emerging question

What are the real organ levels in humans?
(Did we estimate them correctly?)

Measured TiO₂ particle concentration in post-mortem human liver and spleen

- 15 post-mortem liver and spleen
 - Recorded age, gender, ethnicity
- Analysis (by RIKILT)
 - weighed and minced
 - acid digestion of a minced sample, total Ti measured with ICP-HRMS
 - Depolymerisation and protein digestion, measurement of TiO₂ particles with sp-ICP-HRMS
 - SEM-EDX analysis of minced piece
- Method for Ti and TiO₂ analysis validated (by RIKILT)

Risk assessment with measured levels: results

Comparison to model predictions: liver

Comparison to model predictions: spleen

Spleen

Discussion TiO₂ in human liver and spleen

- Still may miss particles <85 nm
- Size range particles in organs (i.e. 86-421 and 88-445 nm) falls within that of particles in food products (30-600 nm diameter)
 - Particles can be single nanoparticles as well as aggregates/agglomerates
 - ≥24% of particles nanosize (< 100 nm)
- It can be assumed that these levels come from oral exposure

Whole risk assessment:

- Extrapolation from short-term studies
- All NP sizes lumped together, and assumed any toxicity is caused only by NPs

Conclusions RIVM work

TiO₂ (nano)particles are present in human liver and spleen

The liver Ti/TiO₂ concentrations in humans are below the liver concentrations related to adverse effects in toxicity studies. However, the MoE_i is limited, thus **risk cannot be excluded**.

If adverse (liver) effects occur due to exposure to TiO₂ remains unclear. Hazard studies have limitations.

Risk assessment of NPs better based on internal concentrations

Closer look on liver effects: mechanisms

Recommendation

- Further (sub)chronic oral toxicity study with TiO_2 as used in food
 - Include determination of tissue concentrations
 - Include markers of liver damage and liver pathology
 - Apply benchmark dose approach to get a good dose-response curve which includes both lower dose groups that are more representative for human exposure as well as higher dose groups
 - > Small particles may agglomerate at higher doses leading to a decrease in the fraction absorbed.
- KRISS performed oral 90-d study (GLP, OECD TG 408)
 - No internal concentrations
 - OECD TG 408: measure >2 of 5 enzymes as marker of liver toxicity

Present

I. EOGRT test was requested by EFSA ANS Panel, based on 2016 evaluation, now awaiting results.

II. Intestine results:

- Urrutia-Ortega et al. (2016), Bettini et al. (2017) and Ruiz et al. (2017): TiO_2 exacerbates colitis, causes tumours in colitis-induced mice, causes increase in intestinal lesions in healthy mice.
 - Proquin et al. (2018): gene expression changes in colon after TiO_2 exposure
- Can TiO_2 NP (and thus E171) cause colon cancer? (analogy with lung cancer?)
- 3 underlying questions identified

Question 1: absorption in colon?

- Ruiz et al. (2017), mouse: No TiO_2 in colon, only in small intestine
 - Induced colitis worsened (in colon)
- Bettini et al. (2017), rat: TiO_2 in cells of PP and in colon mucosa
 - Initiation and promotion of preneoplastic lesions in colon
- Urrutia-Ortega et al. (2016), mouse: TiO_2 in colon cells
 - only colon investigated: preneoplastic lesions in distal colon and particles in colon cells
- Proquin et al. (2018), mouse: TiO_2 not analyzed
 - only distal colon investigated: gene expression changes and hyperplasia

→ Why inconsistency in detection TiO_2 in colon cells?

→ Is absorption in colon cells necessary?

Question 2: genotoxic mechanism (initiation)?

- Analysis genotoxicity Möller et al. (2017): WoE *in vitro* points to DNA strand breaking potential, *in vivo* insufficient quality data
- Meta-analysis *in vitro* genotoxicity data by Charles et al (2018): unclear if genotoxic potential (88 tests in 36 publications included after quality check)
- GCCT 2018: *in vitro* comet assay not reliable, *in vitro* MN only with some additional requirements, for *in vivo* MN assay show exposure of bone marrow/erythrocytes

Shareen Doak: seems to be indirect mechanism:

Current *in vitro* tests not built to pick up indirect genotox → 3D?

NANOMATERIAL GENOTOXICITY TESTING ROADMAP

Q3: immunotoxic mechanism (progression)?

Two possible mechanisms hypothesized in literature:

1. Inflammation → cell death → tissue renewal through cell divisions → increased chance mutations are formed and passed on → tumour cells
2. Proquin et al. 2018: immune suppression → tumour cells not destroyed → more tumours

Impression: hardly information on immune suppression: data gap?

AOP inflammation

- Question for participants: how much evidence is there for this mechanism?

Conclusion on current data gaps

- Reprotox, specifically fertility part
- (sub)chronic oral study with internal conc., according to OECD TG, with E171/anatase
 - Include all measurable events of AOPs
- Appropriate genotoxicity study? For different types of TiO₂ NPs
 - First review exact state of data
 - In vivo desirable due to indirect effects
- Immune suppression study
- Review evidence for inflammation pathway? → possibly specific studies recommended

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Co-authors:

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Min. VWS (Kees Planken) was also closely involved.

July 5th 2018, Amsterdam

Workshop on Possible adverse effects of food additive E171 (titanium dioxide)

Inflammatory responses induced by titanium dioxide in the gut

Gerhard Rogler, Department of Gastroenterology and Hepatology, UniversitätsSpital Zürich

UniversitätsSpital
Zürich

Universität
Zürich^{UZH}

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD)

- **Chronic, relapsing autoinflammation of the colon**
- **Comprises Colitis ulcerosa and Morbus Crohn**
- **Increasing prevalence**
- **Switzerland: 12.000 – 15.000 adult cases**
- **Severe morbidity / restrictions on quality of life**
- **Insufficient treatment options / medication**

- **Causative factor remains unknown**
- **Multifactorial disease – environmental influences – polygenic risk variants**

Understanding IBD pathogenesis is essential to improve conditions for patients and health care

Environmental factors and the incidence and course of IBD

Lifestyle/Environmental factors
in industrialized
countries
70%

„genetic
susceptibility“
30%

Potential mechanisms of diet: Inflammasome-activation via anorganic particles (not just microbiota)

Administration of TiO₂ nanoparticles aggravates DSS colitis

Administration of TiO₂ nanoparticles aggravates DSS colitis

Administration of TiO₂ nanoparticles aggravates DSS colitis

TiO₂ nanoparticles accumulate between enterocytes

Aggregates of TiO₂ accumulate in macrophages and intestinal epithelial cells (IECs).

Aggregates of TiO₂ accumulate in IECs

Caspase-1 downstream effectors are activated in macrophages and intestinal epithelial cells (IECs) on exposure to TiO₂

Aggregates of TiO₂ accumulate in IECs

TiO₂ triggers production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and influences epithelial permeability

The immune-stimulating effect is not “specific” for TiO₂

Patients with IBD present elevated titanium levels in blood

Inflammasome («TiO2 receptor») and PTPN-22

Men: CD patients reveal increased IL18 and IL1β beta levels

Mice: PTPN22 KO results in increased NLRP3 phosphorylation and decreased activation

R619W variant enables faster and more efficient NLRP3 dephosphorylation and subsequent activation

Pizarro et al. J Immunol. 1999, Schmidt et al. Int J Colorectal Dis. 2007, Spalinger et al. JCI. 2016, Spalinger et al. Autophagy 2017, Dai et al. JCI 2013

Present reasearch activities

- Investigate the correlation between environmental factors and genetic risk variants in IBD pathology
- Characterize the role PTPN22 is playing in regulating TiO2 mediated inflammasome activity
- Decode the protective mechanism of the R619W variant and its potential to modulate inflammasome activity
- Depict the systemic effects of TiO2 in different organs, especially in the GIT

What are the new findings?

- ▶ Oral administration of titanium dioxide nanoparticles worsens intestinal inflammation in the dextran sodium sulfate (DSS) mouse model of colitis.
- ▶ Titanium dioxide crystals accumulate in the spleen of DSS-treated mice following oral gavage.
- ▶ Titanium dioxide particles accumulate and activate the NLRP3 inflammasome in human intestinal epithelial cells and macrophages.
- ▶ Levels of titanium are increased in the blood of patients with IBD.

How might it impact on clinical practice in the foreseeable future?

- ▶ Components of the inflammasome may represent novel therapeutic targets for the treatment of IBD.
- ▶ Our results suggest a cautionary use of titanium dioxide in pharmaceutical formulations and support a therapeutic benefit from low inorganic particle diet in patients with IBD.

Thank you for your attention!

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Workshop on possible adverse effects of food additive TiO_2

Amsterdam, July 5-6th, 2018

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Netherlands Food and Consumer
Product Safety Authority
Ministry of Agriculture,
Nature and Food Quality

***Fate and long-term effects of E171
in the GI tract under « normal » conditions***

INRA
SCIENCE & IMPACT

Fate of E171 into the gastrointestinal (GI) tract : the intestine as first target !

Gut : an underestimated target in the toxicity assessment of chemicals !

... often considered as an « entry » for xenobiotics, i.e., the absorption site (**bioavailability**) before distribution in the organism / elimination (**toxicokinetic**), with studies dedicated to systemic effects (**hazard characterization** for development, reprotox, neurotox [...]).

Mucus Goblet cells (mucin secretion)
Mucus layer: 40-300µm thickness in human

Trapping properties *or* local reservoir ?

Microbiota

10¹²⁻¹⁴ micro-organisms
 digestion, immune system homeostasy, barrier to pathogens...

Mainly in the colon !
 slow transit = resident bacteria

Dysbiosis (ecology/activity) ?
 Immune system dysfunction,
 metabolic diseases, brain activity....

Epithelium

Gut barrier
 towards bacteria, viruses, xenobiotics...

Host homeostasy
 nutrient/water absorption,
 hydro-electrolytic exchanges

NP translocation ?
 Barrier dysfunction ?
 Colorectal cancer ?

Immune system

Gut-Associated Lymphoid Tissue (GALT)

Oral tolerance / Host defenses

Allergy-Intolerance / Susceptibility to inflammation ?

Workshop on possible adverse effects of food additive TiO₂

Amsterdam, July 5-6th, 2018

Data from :

(1) SCIENTIFIC REPORTS

OPEN Food-grade TiO₂ impairs intestinal and systemic immune homeostasis, initiates preneoplastic lesions and promotes aberrant crypt development in the rat colon

Received: 13 June 2016
Accepted: 06 December 2016
Published: 20 January 2017

Sarah Bettini¹, Elisa Boutet-Robinet¹, Christel Cartier², Christine Coméra³, Eric Gaultier¹, Jacques Dupuy¹, Nathalie Naud¹, Sylviane Taché³, Patrick Grysan¹, Solenn Reguer¹, Nathalie Thieriet⁴, Matthieu Réfrégiers⁵, Dominique Thiaudière¹, Jean-Pierre Cravedi¹, Marie Carrière^{5,6}, Jean-Nicolas Audinot², Fabrice H. Pierre², Laurence Guzyjack-Pirou² & Eric Houdeau¹

(2)

frontiers in Microbiology

ORIGINAL RESEARCH
published: 24 April 2018
doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2018.00794

Toxicity of Food-Grade TiO₂ to Commensal Intestinal and Transient Food-Borne Bacteria: New Insights Using Nano-SIMS and Synchrotron UV Fluorescence Imaging

Joanna M. Radziwill-Bienkowska¹, Pauline Talbot², Jasper B. J. Kamphuis³, Véronique Robert², Christel Cartier², Isabelle Fourquaux⁴, Esther Lentzen⁵, Jean-Nicolas Audinot², Frédéric Jamme⁶, Matthieu Réfrégiers⁶, Jacek K. Bardowski¹, Philippe Langella², Magdalena Kowalczyk¹, Eric Houdeau², Muriel Thomas² and Muriel Mercier-Bonin^{2*}

(3)

Talbot et al. / Nanobiotechnol. (2018) 16:53
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12951-018-0379-5>

Journal of Nanobiotechnology

RESEARCH Open Access

Food-grade TiO₂ is trapped by intestinal mucus in vitro but does not impair mucin O-glycosylation and short-chain fatty acid synthesis in vivo: implications for gut barrier protection

Pauline Talbot¹, Joanna M. Radziwill-Bienkowska², Jasper B. J. Kamphuis³, Karine Steenkeste⁴, Sarah Bettini³, Véronique Robert², Marie-Louise Noordine¹, Camille Mayeur¹, Eric Gaultier¹, Philippe Langella¹, Catherine Robbe-Masselot⁵, Eric Houdeau¹, Muriel Thomas¹ and Muriel Mercier-Bonin^{2*}

Researchs conducted in the frame of :

NanoGut anses
PNR-EST-2013-024

and,
Grant from INRA Division
Human Nutrition, Food Safety and Consumer Behaviour

E171 vs. P25 NM105 : characterization of particle size and crystal form

Bettini *et al* (2017) **Scientific Reports**

C

	Z average	PdI	ζ (mV)
NM-105	192.23 ± 5.43	0.133 ± 0.014	5.013 ± 0.025
E171	373.5 ± 20.22	0.316 ± 0.048	-23.9 ± 2.36

EDX with doubled count time for « trace elements » : **TiO₂ close to purity**

E171 vs. P25 NM105 : methods used for dispersion and treatments

Bettini *et al* (2017) **Scientific Reports**

NANOGEN TOX

2.56 mg/ml NM Stock Suspension
in EtOH / BSA
(instilled, diluted or dosed into
specific test mediums)

Ultrasonication with probe
preliminary tests 10 vs.16 min
at 30% amplitude

Hydrodynamic diameter (DLS) with time (ultrasonicated TiO₂ re-suspended in water)

- **for chronic oral study in rats** : renewal of the E171 suspension in drinking water **every 2 days**
- **for *in vitro* studies** : stock suspensions always prepared fresh prior to each experiment

Fate of TiO_2 particles along the gut lumen
from interaction with bacteria (food-borne and commensals)
to trapping by the mucus layer
(E171 vs. P25 NM105)

Bettini *et al* (2017) **Scientific Reports**

Radziwill-Bienkowska *et al* (2018) **Frontiers in Microbiology**

Talbot *et al* (2018) **Journal of Nanobiotechnology**

Fate of E171 into the gut lumen : no re-agglomeration in vivo

Bettini *et al* (2017) **Scientific Reports**

In vitro, TiO₂-NP model
re-agglomerate in large clusters (>1µm) in artificial gastric (pepsin/HCl, pH 2) and intestinal (pepsin/HCl, pancreatin and bile extracts, pH 7) phases.

Brun *et al* (2014) Part Fibre Toxicol

In vivo ? →

TiO₂ matter size (4h after a single dose in rats) evaluated by confocal microscopy from suspensions spread on glass slides :

- **Similar dispersion state** from the initial water suspensions (b) to luminal contents recovered from the small (c) and large intestine (d).

Laser reflection of TiO₂ was detected with a **magnification given 1 pixel = 50 nm**

Fate of E171 into the gut lumen : interactions with bacteria

Bacterial strains

TABLE 1 | List of bacterial strains under study.

Species	Strain	Gram characteristics	Origin	commensal intestinal
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	K12 MG1655	Gram-negative	Laboratory strain	
	ATCC8739		Commensal, isolated from infant feces	
	CEC15		Commensal, isolated from a conventional suckling rat intestine	
<i>Lactobacillus rhamnosus</i>	GG	Gram-positive	Commensal, isolated from a healthy human intestine	
<i>Lactobacillus sakei</i>	23K	Gram-positive	Food (meat)	
<i>Lactococcus lactis</i> subsp. <i>cremoris</i>	IBB477	Gram-positive	Food (raw milk)	
<i>Lactococcus lactis</i> subsp. <i>lactis</i>	TIL448		Food (peas)	
<i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i>	LMD-9	Gram-positive	Food (yogurt)	

food-borne

Cell viability

Deep UV Synchrotron excitation TiO₂ (P25 and E171) / bacteria colocalization

Bacteria / Titanium

Yellow (arrowheads) when signals merge

Fate of E171 into the gut lumen : interactions with bacteria

Radziwill-Bienkowska *et al* (2018) *Frontiers in Microbiology*

Bacterial strains

TABLE 1 | List of bacterial strains under study.

Species	Strain	Gram characteristics	Origin	commensal intestinal
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	K12 MG1655	Gram-negative	Laboratory strain	
	ATCC8739		Commensal, isolated from infant feces	
	CEC15		Commensal, isolated from a conventional suckling rat intestine	
<i>Lactobacillus rhamnosus</i>	GG	Gram-positive	Commensal, isolated from a healthy human intestine	
<i>Lactobacillus sakei</i>	23K	Gram-positive	Food (meat)	
<i>Lactococcus lactis</i> subsp. <i>cremoris</i>	IBB477	Gram-positive	Food (raw milk)	
<i>Lactococcus lactis</i> subsp. <i>lactis</i>	TIL448		Food (peas)	
<i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i>	LMD-9	Gram-positive	Food (yogurt)	

food-borne

Morphological damages

Bacterial growth (e.g., *E. coli*)

■ control, × 32.0, ● 62.5, ▲ 125.0, ◆ 320.0 µg/mL
(light colors = dispersed; dark colors = no dispersion)

- ✓ Delayed bacterial growth (bacteriostatic) *and* altered cell viability whatever the strain (E171 > P25)
- ✓ *E. coli* exposed to the food additive E171 showed the most striking effects
- ✓ Consequences under chronic conditions (long-term exposure in human)?

Fate of E171 into the gut lumen : interactions with the mucus layer

Talbot *et al* (2018) *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*

(schema from Béduneau *et al* (2014) *Eur J Pharm Biopharm*)

Evolution of TiO₂-fluorescence intensity over time :

- ✓ Accumulation of TiO₂ particles into the mucus layer
- ✓ Region-specific accumulation (e.g., present in **Area 1** / absent in **Area 2**), where particle matter « sticks on » islets of secreted mucins (18-20 µm above the cell surface)
- ✓ In rats exposed to E171 (60 days) : no effect on mucin *O*-glycosylation *in vivo* (oligosaccharride are « sugars » for commensal bacteria, and adhesion sites for them)
- ✓ No mucus barrier impairment in a healthy gut, but « trapping » properties, possibly increasing TiO₂ particle contact to epithelial surface (with or without absorption?)

Lumen-to-mucosal passage of (nano)TiO₂ particles
from the small to the large bowell, then the liver
(E171 vs. P25 NM105, 1 week per os)

Absorption along the gut : single dose studies

Human volunteers

Single oral dose (≈ 1 mg/kg BW)
 TiO₂ detected in blood

Pele *et al* (2015) Part Fibre Toxicol

- ✓ Rapid passage to the bloodstream (from 1-2h)
- ✓ Bimodal pattern of TiO₂ particle uptake :
 - enterocytes/ villusities (visible by 2h after ingestion)
 - Peyer' patches (retention time / peak at 6h)

Mice

Single oral dose (40 mg/kg BW)
 Comera *et al* (to be published)

E171 or TiO_2 -NP model in Peyer's patches : nanoSIMS analyses

Bettini *et al* (2017) Scientific Reports

Subcellular Ti distribution into immune cells

Mass spectrometry detection of $^{48}Ti^{16}O$ clusters

(1 pixel \approx 80-100 nm / Scale bars 5 μ m)

E171 = P25 NM-105

Intestine and mineral particles/additives

low absorption (<1%) *but* local accumulation with age

Metal oxide particle accumulation in Peyer's patches in Humans

AlSi (E559)
TiO₂ (E171)
SiO₂ (E551)

Mesenteric lymph nodes (MLN)

- Lymphocytes T (Tnaifs Th1, Th2, Th17, Treg)
- ★ Cellules dendritiques (*antigen-presenting cells*)
- Bactéries commensales (microbiote)
- Antigènes alimentaires
- Plasmocytes (lymphocytes B = anticorps)

Clinical data

Powell *et al.* Gut, 1996
Powell *et al.* Brit J Nutr, 2007
Butler *et al.* Inflamm Res, 2007
Hummel *et al.* 2014

Large intestine : absorption in the colon after repeated exposure

TEM-EDX
TiO₂ particles

hot points (Ti)
1 pixel = 10 μm

E171 10mg/kg BW/d
by gastric gavage
(200 μl in water)
for 7 days

Intercellular space
between enterocytes
by TEM

Gut-to-liver passage : systemic distribution

Bettini *et al* (2017) Scientific Reports

Effects on local and systemic immune system
one week vs. 100-day treatment

Immune cell frequency in PP: Bettini et al 2017

Dendritic cells frequency ↗
activated antigen-presenting cells
 (i.e. CD11b/c⁺ CD103⁺ expressing the major histocompatibility complex **MHC-II⁺** on their surfaces for antigen presentation) :

TRANSIENT effect
E171 = P25 NM-105

i.e., return to basal after 100 days of E171 treatment

Tregs cells ↘
 (CD4⁺ CD25⁺ FoxP3⁺)
immunosuppressive activity (IL-10, TGFβ) :
 They organize oral tolerance to food antigens, **self-tolerance**, and regulate inflammatory responses

CHRONIC effect
E171 >> P25 NM-105

Total T cells ↘
 (CD4⁺ CD25⁺)
include T-helper (Th)1 + Th2 + Th17 + Tregs

Dose-dependent cytotoxicity on T cells : Bettini et al 2017

Bettini et al (2017) Scientific Reports

E171 >> P25 NM-105
on T cells isolated from naive* Peyer's patches
*normal rats, i.e., untreated with TiO_2

- Food grade TiO_2 (E171) more cytotoxic than TiO_2 -NP model (P25 NM-105) on total T cells *ex vivo* (Th1, Th2, Th17, Tregs)
- Data in support of *in vivo* observations

Immune cell response : Bettini et al 2017

Mucosal inflammation after 100 days : no IBD-like conditions

E171
only

after 100 days

Lamina propria in the colon (*effector site* of proinflammatory processes)

c

➤ **LOW GRADE** inflammation in the colon (i.e., **NO SIGNIFICANT CHANGES** in IFN- γ , IL-6, IL-18, IL-1 β cytokine levels)

➤ **NO inflammasome activation** (i.e., caspase cleavage) at this level of dose/in the absence of other inflammatory conditions (**CORRELATES NO CHANGES** in the downstream production of IL-18 and IL-1 β cytokines)

Conclusion (1)

- **Food-grade TiO₂ *per os*** in rats at a human relevant dietary level,
 - A source of TiO₂-NPs for the intestinal mucosa (and beyond for the remaining organism)
 - Translocate to immune cells in Peyer's patches (similarly to NP model).
- **E171 absorption is not “neutral”** for the organism through,
 - Imbalance of immune homeostasis in the gut (drop in Treg frequency and Th1 responses),
 - Th1/Th17 immune deviation in splenocytes, suggesting susceptibility to proinflammatory responses at the systemic level (e.g., when face with inflammatory stimuli).
- **Low-grade inflammation** in the colon mucosa after chronic exposure,
 - increase in basal cytokine levels / no sign of IBD-like (acute) inflammation,
 - no inflammasome activation at 10 mg/kg BW/day.

Similar observation in a mouse model orally exposed to E171 (same batch *and* dose) for 60 days by gastric gavage *unpublished*

Colon
Fecal lipocaline (LCN2)

**Effects on the initiation and promotion
of preneoplastic lesions in the colon**
oral treatment for 100 days in rats (E171 only)
in vitro studies (E171 vs. P25 NM105)

Models and strategy used : a strategy trying to « link » size-to-effects

GOAL : to assess whether E171 is a **risk factor** in the **initiation and/or promotion of colonic preneoplastic lesions** (i.e., the first stages of colorectal cancer development, **not tumor formation**).

How ? E171 orally administered to rats for **100 days at 2 doses** (200 µg and/or 10 mg/kg of BW per day) through drinking water,

ACF

➤ *In vivo* assessment of **spontaneous development and/or promotion of preneoplastic lesions** (Aberrant Crypt Foci, ACF) in the rat colon

- **Initiation** : without dimethylhydrazine (DMH)-induced carcinogenesis
- **Promotion**: with DMH induction

ACF of 2 crypts at the colonic mucosal surface stained with methylene blue (40X)

- **ACF** were counted under light microscope (fixation with 10% buffered formalin + methylene blue tissue staining), **in duplicate by two independent readers, blinded for the origin of the colon.**
 - **Number of lesions per colon** : ACF / colon
 - **Size of lesions** : Crypts / Foci
 - **Number of aberrant crypts per colon** : i.e., preneoplastic load = AC/colon
- **Statistics**: t-test *and* contingency test for 2 comparison groups (**initiation**) and ANOVA for 3 comparison groups (**promotion**)

Promotion of preneoplastic lesions : effect of dose exposure

Bettini *et al* (2017) Scientific Reports

- Effect on the number of ACF per colon : no significant difference between groups
- Effect on the preneoplastic load (AC per colon)

Promotion of the lesional load by E171

effect not observed at the lower dose

- Effect on the number of large ACF (≥ 4 crypts)

Promotion of number of large ACF by E171

effect not observed at the lower dose

* Significantly different of controls : ANOVA and Fisher's Least-Significant-Difference Test

- The food grade TiO₂ (E171, ultrasonicated OR NOT) **PROMOTES** preneoplastic lesions in the rat colon, at 10 mg/kg BW/d for 100 days.
- Not observed at a lower dose (200 µg/kg BW/d).

Initiation of preneoplastic lesions

Number of rats with or without preneoplastic lesions after 100 days of E171 exposure

ACF of 2 and 12 crypts

ACF at the colonic mucosal surface stained with methylene blue (40X)

- The food grade TiO_2 (ultrasonicated E171) **INDUCES** preneoplastic lesions in the rat colon, at 10 mg/kg BW/d for 100 days.

Conclusion (2)

- Oral exposure to food-grade TiO_2 , at a representative dose of human exposure, **induces** and **promotes preneoplastic lesions** in the colon after chronic exposure (100 days)
- These effects were observed on :
 - the **lesional load** (total number of aberrant crypts per colon),
 - the **number of large preneoplastic lesions** (size of ACF)
- Effect correlated with (*but* no causal demonstration) :
 - a **developing “low-grade inflammation”** into the colonic mucosa,
 - a **positive selection of pre-neoplastic cells** and **genotoxicity on normal cells** *in vitro* (please see Bettini *et al* suppl data - effect similar to TiO_2 -NP model)
- Insufficient to conclude on a risk at the tumor stage :
 - **need Carcinogenicity studies** according to OECD guidelines #451,
 - **focus on E171 displaying a large fraction of nanoparticulate matter** (i.e., $\geq 40\%$)

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Promotion of colon cancer by E171

Dra. Yolanda Irasema Chirino

**Workshop on Possible adverse
effects of food additive E171 (titanium dioxide)**

Amsterdam, the Netherlands

July 5-6, 2018

Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México

Outline

1. Introduction
2. Hypothesis & Aim of our first study
3. Results
4. Conclusions
5. Research ongoing (solid vs liquid E171 administration)

1. Introduction

Evidence of TiO₂ in food products

NIH Public Access

Author Manuscript

Environ Sci Technol. Author manuscript; available in PMC 2013 February 21.

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Environ Sci Technol. 2012 February 21; 46(4): 2242–2250. doi:10.1021/es204168d.

NIH-PA Author Manuscript

Titanium Dioxide Nanoparticles in Food and Personal Care Products

Alex Weir¹, Paul Westerhoff^{1,*}, Lars Fabricius^{2,3}, and Natalie von Goetz²

Evidence of TiO₂ deposits in humans

Figure 4: Pigmented cell, reprocessed from wax blocks, viewed by transmission electron microscopy (original $\times 8200$). The cell nucleus (N) and distinct intravesicular areas of microparticles (for example P) are apparent. The extracellular material appears to be mainly collagen (C) and also shown is probably a plasma cell (top right).

Department of Histopathology, Royal Free Hospital School of Medicine, London, England presented this medical findings in 1996.

10 patients with Crohn's disease
5 patients with ulcerative colitis
5 patients with colonic carcinoma

Figure 6: Typical x ray microanalysis spectra from: an aluminium and silicon containing particle also with some iron (A), and a silicon containing particle without aluminium also with some magnesium (B). The copper peaks are from the grid, titanium and uranium from the fixative and stain, and potassium and chlorine from the tissue and resin. These three peaks were shown to be background by analysing away from such particles (C). A typical spectrum from a titanium containing particle is also shown (D).

X ray analysis showed the presence of titanium.

Evidence of TiO₂ deposits in humans

Pigment deposits in Peyer's Patches of patients with IBD (Thoree et al., 2008)

Department of Histopathology, St Thomas' Hospital, London, SE1 7EH, UK

16 patients with adenocarcinoma
23 with Crohn's disease
10 non-colitis

TiO₂ and aluminum deposits in Peyer's Patches in children with IBD (Hummel et al., 2014)

Department of Pediatric Gastroenterology and Nutrition, Academic Medical Center, Amsterdam, The Netherlands

62 with Crohn disease (CD)
26 with ulcerative colitis
63 with non-IBD

In 63 children (42%), deposits of black pigment were found only in biopsies from the terminal ileum, located in Peyer patches.

2A. HYPOTHESIS

Administration of E171 enhanced the tumors formation in colon in a colorectal cancer model in mice after 10 weeks of exposure.

2B. AIM

To evaluate the E171 effect by intragastric administration dosed at 5mg/bw/10w in a colorectal cancer mice model induced chemically by axoxymethane/DSS.

Experimental design

3. RESULTS

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Food and Chemical Toxicology

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/foodchemtox

Food-grade titanium dioxide exposure exacerbates tumor formation in colitis associated cancer model

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

ABSTRACT

Colorectal cancer is the fourth worldwide cause of death and even if some dietary habits are consider risk

Physicochemical properties of E171 (food grade titanium dioxide)

A

Raman Spectrum

E171

SEM

TEM

Characterization of E171. A) Representative Raman shift, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of primary particles of E171 and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) of E171 agglomerates dispersed water. B) Polydispersity index of E171 agglomerates shows hydrodynamic diameter distribution by tracking analysis and C) Z potential titration of E171 agglomerates.

E171 had no effects on body weight, food intake nor water consumption

Intragastric E171 administration enhanced the tumor formation in distal colon

Intragastric E171 exposure increased tumor formation. Tumor formation count after 72 days of treatment. CAC+E171 group had increased tumor compared to CAC group (** $p \leq 0.01$ vs CAC).

Intragastric E171 administration enhanced tumor formation and induced pre-neoplastic alterations in colon

Fig 5. Dysplasia in CAC tumors and colon tissue increased by E171 intragastric exposure. Representative colonic histopathology in experimental groups. A) Control group exhibit normal epithelium and colorectal crypts. B) E171 group show an increase of crypts size and number, revisited with hyperplastic epithelium with slight dysplastic changes. Polypoid well differentiated adenocarcinoma in a mouse from C) CAC group, numerous glands with irregular sizes revisited with dysplastic epithelium. Irregular neoplastic glands revisited with hyperplastic stratified cubic epithelium showing dysplastic changes and solid areas with neoplastic cells (asterisk) is observed in the D) CAC+E171 group. In the inset, a higher power magnification micrograph shows dysplastic epithelium, large cells with hyperchromatic nucleus.

Intragastric E171 exposure reduced the content of goblet cells

Intragastric E171 exposure reduced number of goblet cells in colon tissue. Goblet cells were stained in blue and marked with a dagger in groups A) Control B) E171, C) CAC and D) CAC+E171. E) Goblet cells in colon decreased with the sole E171 administration, but also in CRC group, however, CAC+E171 treatment had higher decrease in those cells. Detection was performed by Alcian blue staining and blind count was realized in each colon sample. Data are presented as mean±SEM; * $p < 0.01$.

Intragastric E171 exposure enhanced tumor progression markers

Hoechst Ki67 MERGE

Ct

E171

CAC

CAC+ E171

D

Intragastric E171 exposure enhanced tumor progression markers

E

F

Colonic cells internalized E171 particles and cell retained the particles under ex-vivo cell culture

Intragastric E171 exposure decrease kidney mass in mice with colorectal cancer

4. Conclusions

Intragastric administration of E171 dispersed in water and dosed at 5mg/kgbw/5days/10weeks enhanced tumor formation in a colorectal cancer mice model chemically induced by AOM/DSS. E171 was unable to induce colon tumors itself but dysplastic changes in colonic epithelium and decreased goblet cells.

Mechanisms of E171 induced adverse reactions in the gut

Prof. dr. Theo M. de Kok
Department of Toxicogenomics, Maastricht University, The Netherlands.

NVWA workshop • 5-6 July 2018 • Amsterdam

Outline

- Potential adverse effects of E171
- Suggested mechanisms of action
- Mechanistic studies in vivo
- Mechanistic studies in vitro
- Concluding remarks

Potential adverse effects of E171

Liver toxicity

Endocrine and reproduction toxicity

Cardiotoxicity

Inflammatory responses

Colorectal tumour promotion

Potential adverse effects of E171

Liver toxicity

Endocrine and reproduction toxicity

Cardiotoxicity

Inflammatory responses

Colorectal tumour promotion

Suggested mechanisms of action

Formation of reactive oxygen species

Resulting in oxidative stress

DNA-damage and inflammatory responses

Exacerbation of pre-existing inflammation

Impairment of intestinal and systemic immune homeostasis

Initiation of preneoplastic lesions and promotion aberrant crypt development

Tumour promotion

Mechanistic studies in vivo

Research questions based on the initial paper of Urrutia-Ortega et al (FCT 2016):

1. What histopathological changes and molecular mechanisms are affected after E171 ingestion in normal mice?
2. What molecular mechanisms are affected after E171 ingestion in AOM exposed mice?
3. Are the same molecular mechanisms affected in a transgenic mouse model without chemical induction of tumours?

Mechanistic studies in vivo (normal mice)

Research questions based on the initial paper of Urrutia-Ortega et al (FCT 2016):

1. What histopathological changes and molecular mechanisms are affected after E171 ingestion in normal mice?
2. What molecular mechanisms are affected after E171 ingestion in AOM exposed mice?
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Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

Food and Chemical Toxicology

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/foodchemtox

Gene expression profiling in colon of mice exposed to food additive titanium dioxide (E171)

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- BALB/c mice were exposed by gavage to 5 mg/kg_{bw}/day of E171
- for 2, 7, 14, and 21 days;
- Whole genome mRNA microarray analysis on distal colons
- Histopathological changes and proliferation were analysed.

Mechanistic studies in vivo (normal mice)

Histopathological analysis showed alteration and **disruption** in the normal structure of crypts inducing a **hyperplastic** epithelium.

At cell proliferation level (Ki67 expression), no consistent increase over time was observed.

Mechanistic studies in vivo (normal mice)

Gene expression analysis:

Differentially expressed genes ($p < 0.05$ and $FC > 1.5$) between the different time points (2, 7, 14, and 21 days) after exposure to E171 in colon of mice.

Mechanistic studies in vivo (normal mice)

Pathway analysis per time point:

- E171 regulated GPCR/olfactory receptors, involved in cancer signaling;
- induced oxidative stress and immune response pathways,
- activated genes for DNA repair;
- both up- and down-regulated genes involved in development of colon cancer.

Modulation of genes that thus far have not been defined as being involved in any pathway.

Mechanistic studies in vivo

Research questions based on the initial paper of Urrutia-Ortega et al (FCT 2016):

1. What histopathological changes and molecular mechanisms are affected after E171 ingestion in normal mice?
2. What are the molecular mechanisms behind the tumour stimulatory effects of E171 in combination with azoxymethane (AOM)/dextran sodium sulphate (DSS)?
3. Are the same molecular mechanisms affected in a transgenic mouse model without chemical induction of tumours?

OPEN

Transcriptomics analysis reveals new insights in E171-induced molecular alterations in a mouse model of colon cancer

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- BALB/c mice were exposed by gavage to 5 mg/kg_{bw}/day of E171
- for 2, 7, 14, and 21 days;
- Whole genome mRNA microarray analysis on distal colons

Hypothesis: oral intake of E171 induces gene expression changes related to inflammation, deregulation of cancer-related genes and impairment of the immune system **before tumours are detectable.**

Mechanistic studies (AOM/DSS mouse model)

Gene expression analysis:

Differentially expressed genes ($p < 0.05$ and $FC > 1.5$) between the different time points (2, 7, 14, and 21 days) after exposure to E171 in colon of mice.

- Pathway analysis per time point
- Time series analyses
- Time point comparisons
- Time course network analysis

Pathways derived from the over-representation analysis (ORA) at different time points of exposure to E171.

Mechanistic studies (AOM/DSS mouse model)

At all time points, E171 affected mRNA levels related to:

- signaling (GPCR, olfactory, cytokine, cancer signaling)
- immune system (innate and adaptive).

Mechanistic studies (AOM/DSS mouse model)

Time course network analysis based on the pathway analyses as well as relevant DEG over time

→ Comparison between studies with and without AOM induction

- Blue is E171 only
- Red is AOM induced
- Blue/ Red common

Mechanistic studies (AOM/DSS mouse model)

E171 induced a downregulation of genes involved in the innate and adaptive **immune system**, suggesting impairment of this system.

Effects potentially associated with **oxidative stress** were observed through modulation of genes related to antioxidant production.

Over time, **genes involved in (colorectal) cancer signaling** were modulated.

These transcriptomics data reflect the early biological responses induced by E171 which precede tumour formation in an AOM/DSS mouse model.

Mechanistic studies in vivo

Research questions based on the initial paper of Urrutia-Ortega et al (FCT 2016):

1. What histopathological changes and molecular mechanisms are affected after E171 ingestion in normal mice?
2. What are the molecular mechanisms behind the tumour stimulatory effects of E171 in combination with azoxymethane (AOM)/dextran sodium sulphate (DSS)?
3. Are the same molecular mechanisms affected in a transgenic mouse model without chemical induction of tumours?

Mechanistic studies (Transgenic mouse model)

Transgenic mouse model based on the Cre-LoxP system

that provides a colon specific knockout model which spontaneously develops colorectal tumours.

From 5 weeks of age, $CAC^{Tg/Tg};APC^{580S/+}$ mice were treated with

- 5 mg/kg_{bw}/day of E171 (n=40) or
- sterile water as control (n=40)
- for 1, 3, 5, 7 or 9 weeks
- To evaluate tumour formation.

Mechanistic studies (Transgenic mouse model)

This study showed that E171 enhanced the number of mice with tumours as well as the average number of tumours in these mice.

Black bars: control mice exposed to sterile water.
Grey bars exposed to 5 mg/kg bw/day of E171.

Mechanistic studies (Transgenic mouse model)

For gene expression analysis in the colon:

- 140 mice were divided in 4 groups;
- 3 exposure groups with 3 concentrations of E171 (1, 2, and 5 mg/kg_{bw}/day);
- one control group with sterile water;
- Exposure 5 days/week during 2, 7, 14, and 21 days;
- 7 mice per group, 3 females and 4 males.

Mechanistic studies (Transgenic mouse model)

Differentially expressed genes per dose and time point

Mechanistic studies (Transgenic mouse model)

Time course network analysis based on the pathway analyses as well as relevant DEG over time

→ Comparison between studies with and without AOM induction and the transgenic mouse model

- Blue is E171 only
- Red is AOM induced
- Orange is transgenic
- Blue/ Red / Orange in common

Mechanistic studies (Transgenic mouse model)

This model confirms the earlier findings that E171

- downregulates of genes involved in the innate and adaptive **immune system**, suggesting impairment of this system.
- Induces effects associated with **oxidative stress**
- Modulates **cancer signaling genes**.

The combination of these effects may lead to the enhancement of tumour development in transgenic mice.

In vitro mechanistic studies

Findings from only a few previous studies on **E171** show:

- Induction of oxidative stress and oxidative damage to DNA in **human** Caco-2 colon cell culture systems;
- Concomitant downregulation of the expression of the antioxidant enzymes catalase, superoxide dismutase and glutathione reductase.

Dorier-M. et al Nanotoxicology. 2017 Aug;11(6):751-761.

In vitro mechanistic studies

Mutagenesis, 2017, 32, 139–149

doi:10.1093/mutage/gew051

Original Manuscript

Advance Access publication 27 October 2016

OXFORD

Original Manuscript

Titanium dioxide food additive (E171) induces ROS formation and genotoxicity: contribution of micro and nano-sized fractions

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Henk van Loveren¹ and Yolanda I. Chirino²

In vitro mechanistic studies

ROS quantification in Caco-2 exposed cell culture in presence and absence of AOM

In vitro mechanistic studies

DNA damage in Caco-2 cell cultures

In vitro mechanistic studies (micronucleus test)

E171 induced chromosome damage in HCT116 cell cultures

In vitro mechanistic studies

ROS generation in a cell-free environment was highest for E171 followed by NPs and MPs (not shown).

MPs were capable to induce significant ROS formation in exposed Caco-2 cells.

E171, MPs and NPs all induced single-strand DNA breaks.

Chromosome damage was shown to be induced by E171, as tested with the micronucleus assay in HCT116 cells.

In conclusion, these findings confirm the capacity of E171, MP and NP to induce ROS formation and genotoxic effects.

In vitro transcriptomic responses in Caco-2

Time specific responses to TiO₂ NP (2, 4, 24 h)

Most abundant and diverse gene expression and pathway changes after 24h exposure.

Unique and common DEG after exposure of Caco-2 cells to 1.43 µg/cm² E171, MPs, and NPs for 24h.

Biological processes modulated:

- Cellular response to (oxidative) stress
- Innate and adaptive immune system
- Inflammation
- Cell signalling
- Cancer

Concluding remarks

- E171 modulates relevant molecular pathways related to cancer development:
 - Oxidative stress
 - Inflammation
 - Immune response
 - Cancer signaling
- These mechanisms are consistently found in different mouse models as well as in human colon cells.

These mechanisms may play a role in the promotion of tumour development in E171 exposed mice.

Acknowledgement

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Ismaël Urrutia Ortega
Carolina Rodríguez-Ibarra
Yolanda Chirino

Additional slides

Mechanistic studies (normal mouse model)

Mechanistic studies (AOM/DSS mouse model)

In vitro mechanistic studies

ROS quantification in acellular conditions

The EFSA re-evaluation of titanium dioxide

Dr David Gott

Head of Toxicology Team, Food Standards Agency and Member of EFSA
ANS Panel

Views expressed are those of the author and should not be considered to reflect FSA or EFSA policy

Outline of presentation

- Food additives re-evaluation programme
- EFSA opinion on titanium dioxide (2016)
- Conclusions and uncertainties
- New developments: latest EFSA opinion (June 2018)

The EFSA re-evaluation programme

- The following slides are taken from my presentation at the EFSA Stakeholder Workshop in November 2017
- My thanks to the Food Ingredients and Packaging unit for preparing them for that meeting and allowing me to use them today

RE-EVALUATION VS NEW APPLICATIONS

Re-evaluation programme

Reg. 257/2010

Food additives already permitted before

Food additives authorised after

Common authorisation procedure

Reg. 1331/2008

20 Jan 2009

RE-EVALUATION VS NEW APPLICATIONS

Re-evaluation

SCIENTIFIC OPINION

Statement on a conceptual framework for the risk assessment of certain food additives re-evaluated under Commission Regulation (EU) No 257/2010¹

EFSA Panel on Food additives and Nutrient Sources added to Food (ANS)²
European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Parma, Italy

ABSTRACT

The Panel on Food Additives and Nutrient Sources added to Food (ANS) provides a scientific statement presenting a conceptual framework for the risk assessment of certain food additives re-evaluated under Commission Regulation (EU) No 257/2010. This framework will be used in the evaluation made by the Panel, but the expert judgement of the scientific background, on a case-by-case basis, remains essential to reach a final conclusion. The outcome of the re-evaluation of food additives taking into account all available information is presented in the document, as well as the exposure assessment scenarios to be carried out by the Panel considering the use levels set in the legislation and the availability of adequate usage or analytical data.

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KEY WORDS

Commission Regulation (EU) No 257/2010, food additives, re-evaluation, risk assessment

Food additives
already
permitted **before**

Food additives
authorised **after**

New applications

20 Jan 2009

SCIENTIFIC OPINION

Guidance for submission for food additive evaluations¹
EFSA Panel on Food Additives and Nutrient Sources added to Food (ANS)^{2,3}

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Parma, Italy

This Scientific Opinion, published on 16 August 2012, replaces the earlier version published on 18 July 2012.⁴

ABSTRACT

This guidance document refers to the applications for authorisation of a new food additive or to a modification of an already authorised food additive, combining in a single document the description of the data requirements and their context, and also a description of the risk assessment paradigm applied. The document is arranged in four main sections: chemistry and specifications, existing authorisations and evaluations, proposed uses and exposure assessment, and toxicological studies. Assessment of the exposure to food additives is based on information on known or anticipated human exposure to the proposed additive or toxicologically relevant components of the additive from food, and any other potential dietary sources. For the toxicological studies, this guidance document proposes a tiered approach which balances data requirements against the risk, taking into account the welfare by adopting animal testing strategies in line with the 3-Rs (replacement, reduction, refinement). This tiered approach for toxicological studies consists of 3 tiers, for which the testing triggers are described. According to this tiered approach, a minimal dataset has been developed under Tier 1, while Tier 2 testing, generating more extensive data which are absorbed and/or demonstrate (geno)toxicity in Tier 1 tests. Tier 3 testing is conducted on a case-by-case basis taking into consideration all the available data, to elucidate the nature and extent of findings in Tier 2 tests. This guidance document replaces the guidance document published by the Committee for Food published in 2001.

Authorisation, Tiered approach, Risk assessment, Toxicological studies

RE-EVALUATION VS NEW APPLICATIONS

20 Jan 2009

SCIENTIFIC ASSESSMENT

In the re-evaluation of food additives the available pieces of the jigsaw are put together

There may be missing pieces, but can we still understand the picture?

How do we piece together the jigsaw?

- Consider all the data available
- Evaluate the data and the data gaps
- Assess the significance of the data gaps
- Use read across and extrapolation as appropriate
- Use a weight of evidence evaluation
- In considering need for additional studies against uncertainty take account of other societal values e.g. animal welfare

SCIENTIFIC ASSESSMENT

Technical part

- Identity of the substance
- Specifications
- Analytical results
- Manufacturing process
- Methods of analysis in food
- Stability and fate in food

Questions

- What is the food additive?
- Are we talking about the same substance that it was assessed at the time of the initial authorisation?
- What are residuals/by products resulting from manufacturing process/storage/interaction with food?

HAZARD IDENTIFICATION

SCIENTIFIC ASSESSMENT

Biological and toxicological data

- ADME (absorption, metabolism, distribution, excretion)
- Genotoxicity (in vitro, in vivo)
- General toxicity (short-term, sub-chronic, chronic, carcinogenicity)
- Reproductive toxicity
- Immunotoxicity
- Other studies

Questions

- What happens to the additive once it is ingested with the diet? Is it absorbed? To what is it metabolised?
- Are adverse effects identified from the available studies?
- If yes: can a dose response be identified?
- If no: true lack of effect or lack of data?
- Are the data available still reliable compared to today's standards?

HAZARD CHARACTERISATION

SCIENTIFIC ASSESSMENT

Dietary
exposure

- Maximum permitted levels given in the legislation
- Typical uses and use levels
- Analytical data
- Other sources of exposure

Questions

- How much is the daily intake of the food additive in the EU population?
- Are there groups of the population that are exposed to it more than others?
- Is the additive really used in all the food categories in which it is authorised?
- Which food categories contribute most to the exposure?

EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR RE-EVALUATION

Re-evaluation of titanium dioxide E171

- The last food colours to be re-evaluated
 - Number of calls for data
- Previous evaluations
 - JECFA 1969
 - an acceptable daily intake (ADI) 'not limited except for good manufacturing practice'
 - SCF 1977
 - colours for which an ADI was not established but which could be used in food
- Also used as a feed additive: ongoing evaluation by the EFSA FEEDAP Panel

The nanomaterial issue

- All particulate food additives contain a distribution of particle sizes some of which are likely to be in the nano range
- Information provided on E171
 - would not be considered as a nanomaterial according to the EU Recommendation on the definition of a nanomaterial
- Currently no set limits for the particle size of TiO_2 in the EU specifications
- Panel recommended specifications for E 171 should include a characterisation of particle size distribution using appropriate statistical descriptors (e.g. range, median, quartiles) as well as the percentage (in number and by mass) of particles in the nanoscale

During re-evaluation Panel considered

- manufacturing process for powdered or particulate food additives resulted in material with a range of sizes.
- median size of the particles is generally significantly greater than 100 nm, a small fraction will always be, and has been, with at least one dimension below 100 nm
- material used for toxicological testing would have contained this nano fraction.
- in principle, for a specific food additive containing a fraction of particles with at least one dimension below 100 nm, adequately conducted toxicity tests should be able to detect hazards associated with this food additive, including its nanoparticulate fraction
- for the re-evaluation of food additives, this procedure would be sufficient for evaluating constituent nanoform fraction in accordance with the recommendation of the EFSA Nano Network in 2014

How big a problem is it?

- analytical data provided by interested parties confirmed the small percentage in the nanoscale
- BUT actual values depended on the method used
- Based on this information a percentage value of up to 3.2% of nanoparticles by mass was considered a reasonably conservative estimate

ADME conclusions

- the absorption of orally administered TiO_2 is extremely low
- the bioavailability of TiO_2 (measured either as particles or as titanium) is low
- the bioavailability measured as titanium appeared to be independent of particle size
- the vast majority of an oral dose of TiO_2 is eliminated unchanged in faeces
- a small amount (maximum of 0.1%) of orally ingested TiO_2 was absorbed by the GALT and subsequently distributed to various organs and elimination rates from these organs were variable
- there were significant and highly variable background (basal) levels of titanium in animals and humans, which presented challenges in the analysis at the low levels of titanium uptake reported and could complicate interpretation of the reported findings in some studies

short-term and subchronic toxicity

- rather limited information available
- 28-day gavage study in rats, NOAEL for the study was 24,000 mg/kg bw per day **but material was not E171 but** useful as supporting evidence
- 90-day study, doses up to 16,900 mg /kg bw per day for male mice and up to 8,100 mg /kg bw per day for male rats
- No differences in body weight or in relevant gross or microscopic pathology BUT no haematological parameters and no biochemical parameters in urine and blood were measured

Genotoxicity

- available mixed results provided some evidence of *in vitro* genotoxicity for TiO₂ micro- and nanoparticles
 - most positive results have been reported under experimental conditions associated with the induction of oxidative stress
 - genotoxic effects observed mainly in indicator assays, which may not be associated with permanent chromosome damage.
- *In vivo*
 - overall negative results were obtained in genotoxicity studies with microsized
 - Limited, if any, evidence in studies with orally administered nanoparticle
 - Limited or no indication of genotoxicity for nanoparticles using the intravenous route of administration

Carcinogenicity and chronic toxicity

- No evidence of carcinogenicity in rats and mice
 - Studies were old (1979)
 - Limited information on titanium dioxide tested
 - Carried out by US National Cancer Institute
 - Used oral administration
- Evidence of carcinogenicity in inhalation studies but not relevant for this evaluation
- NOAEL was highest dose tested - 50000 mg/kg diet
 - Equivalent to
 - 6,500 and 8,350 mg/kg bw per day, for male and female mice, respectively
 - 2,250 and 2,900 mg/kg bw per day, for male and female rats, respectively

Promotion initiation studies

- Urrutia-Ortega et al. (2016),
- Intragastric administration of TiO₂ (E 171) in a chemically colitis-associated colorectal cancer (CAC) model in 24 mice in 4 groups
 - (a) control;
 - (b) 5 mg/kg bw foodgrade TiO₂ (E 171; 99% pure) by gavage, 5 days/week for 10 weeks;
 - (c) the chemically colitis associated cancer (CAC) group received a single i.p. dose of 12.5 mg/kg bw azoxymethane (AOM) and 2% dextran sulfate sodium (DSS) in the third, sixth and ninth week in water ad libitum;
 - (d) the CAC + TiO₂ (E 171) group: AOM, DSS and TiO₂ (E 171).
- TiO₂ (E 171) in combination with the initiator increased the expression of markers of tumour progression including COX2, Ki67 and b-catenin.
- TiO₂ (E 171) alone did not show any enhancing effect on tumour markers.
- Further research needed but study cannot be used for risk assessment

Reproductive and developmental toxicity

- No reproductive (one- or two-generation toxicity) studies with TiO₂ (as the food additive, micro- or nanosized) performed according to the OECD guidelines were available for evaluation
- prenatal developmental studies with three pigment-grade (pg-1, pg-2 and pg-3) and three ultrafine (uf-1, uf-2 and uf-3)/nanoscale (anatase and/or rutile) TiO₂ particulates performed according to the OECD guidelines (TG 414) did not give concern for maternal or developmental toxicity up to the highest dose tested (1,000 mg/kg bw per day).
- Results from other reproductive and developmental studies with titanium nanoparticles (Jia et al., 2014 and Tassinari et al., 2014) showed contradictory results in the change in hormone levels
- Due to deficiencies in the study designs and inadequate data reporting, relevance of these findings is currently uncertain for the risk assessment

Immunotoxicity

- available studies on the effects of TiO₂ (nano)particles on the immune systems pointed to different outcomes
- reported effects were dependent on
 - the core composition,
 - size and concentration of the particles,
 - and on the duration and route of exposure
- given the absence of clear characterisation of the material used, the difference in effects observed following various routes of administration and the diversity in the effects reported, a conclusion on the possible immunotoxic effects of the food additive TiO₂ cannot be reached
- However, the Panel noted that the larger the TiO₂ particles, the lower their potential to induce effects, and that from animal data it appeared that the route of injection influences the response, TiO₂ particles being less reactive after oral administration

Conclusions on the toxicity database

- based on information reported in the examined literature and information supplied following calls for data
- Considering
 - the food additive E 171 mainly consists of micro-sized TiO₂ particles, with a nanosized (< 100 nm) fraction less than 3.2% by mass;
 - the absorption of orally administered TiO₂ particles (micro- and nanosized) in the gastrointestinal tract is negligible, estimated at most as 0.02–0.1% of the administered dose;
 - no difference is observed in the absorption, distribution, and excretion of orally administered micro-sized and nanosized TiO₂ particles;
 - no adverse effect resulting from the eventual accumulation of the absorbed particles is expected based on the results of long-term studies which did not highlight any toxicity up to the highest administered dose;
 - the uncertainties in the toxicological database arising from limitations in the available reproductive toxicity studies
- an ADI should not be established, and that a margin of safety (MoS) approach would be appropriate

Exposure assessment

- Calculated by two approaches
 - maximum levels provided to EFSA and
 - reported use levels as provided by industry and Member States
- Two scenarios
 - Brand loyal
 - assumed that the population is exposed over a long period of time to the food additive present at the maximum reported use/analytical levels for one food category and to a mean reported use/analytical level for the remaining food categories
 - Non-brand loyal
 - assumed that the population is exposed over a long period of time to the food additive present at the mean reported use/analytical levels in all relevant food categories

The Panel considered

- the refined exposure assessment approach was a more realistic scenario,
 - because it was based on the range of usage and analytical data, assumed that the processed foods and beverages contain the additive at the mean concentration level for all products (non-brand-loyal consumer scenario) and considers one product containing TiO₂ at the maximum concentration level (brand-loyal consumer scenario)
- However
 - due to the low amount of data provided to EFSA (reported use levels or analytical data) only 14 food categories were taken into account, representing between 60% and 80% of food (by weight) authorised to contain TiO₂

Estimated exposures

- Ranges from lowest to highest covering different population groups
- Maximum
 - Mean
 - 0.4 mg/kg bw per day for infants and the elderly to 10.4 mg/kg bw per day for children
 - 95%
 - 1.2 mg/kg bw per day for the elderly to 32.4 mg/kg bw per day for children
- Brand loyal
 - Mean
 - 0.4 mg/kg bw per day for infants and the elderly to 8.8 mg/kg bw per day for children
 - 95%
 - 1.1 mg/kg bw per day for the elderly to 30.2 mg/kg bw per day for children.
- Non-brand loyal
 - Mean
 - 0.2 mg/kg bw per day for infants and the elderly to 5.5 mg/kg bw per day for children.
 - 95%
 - 0.5 mg/kg bw per day for the elderly to 14.8 mg/kg bw per day for children

For risk characterisation

- Considered non-brand-loyal scenario covering the general population was the more appropriate and realistic scenario
- Used these exposures and NOAEL of 2,250 mg TiO₂/kg bw per day from the NCI study to estimate margins of safety
- Guidance for submission of food additives (EFSA ANS Panel, 2012), the Panel considered that, for non-genotoxic and non-carcinogenic compounds “a MoS of 100 or more between a NOAEL or BMDL and the anticipated exposure would be sufficient to account for uncertainty factors for extrapolating between individuals and species”.

Margins of safety

(min–max across the 6 dietary surveys)

Population groups	Mean	95%
Infants	2,800–11,000	600–3,200
Toddlers	500–3,800	350–1,200
Children	400–2,500	150–950
Adolescents	550–5,700	200–1,800
Adults	550–7,500	250–2,100
The elderly	800–11,000	300–4,500

Nanoparticle exposure

- Ranges from lowest to highest covering different population groups using highest reported weight percentage value of 3.2% of nanoparticles by mass
- Maximum
 - Mean
 - 0.01 mg/kg bw per day for infants and the elderly to 0.33 mg/kg bw per day for children
 - 95%
 - 0.04 mg/kg bw per day for infant and the elderly to 1.04 mg/kg bw per day for children
- Brand loyal
 - Mean
 - 0.01 mg/kg bw per day for infants and the elderly to 0.28 mg/kg bw per day for children
 - 95%
 - 0.03 mg/kg bw per day for the elderly to 0.97 mg/kg bw per day for children.
- Non-brand loyal
 - Mean
 - 0.01 mg/kg bw per day for infants, adolescent, adults and the elderly to 0.18 mg/kg bw per day for children.
 - 95%
 - 0.02 mg/kg bw per day for infant and the elderly to 0.47 mg/kg bw per day for children

Overall conclusions

- possible adverse effects in the reproductive system were identified in some studies conducted with material which was either non-food-grade or inadequately characterised nanomaterial (i.e. not E 171).
- There were no such indications in the available, albeit limited, database on reproductive endpoints for the food additive (E 171).
- The Panel was unable to reach a definitive conclusion on this endpoint due to the lack of an extended 90-day study as in the Guidance for submission of food additives (EFSA ANS Panel, 2012) or a multigeneration or extended-one generation reproduction toxicity study with the food additive (E 171).

Therefore

- on the database currently available and the considerations on the absorption of TiO_2 the margins of safety calculated from the NOAEL of 2,250 mg TiO_2 /kg bw per day identified in the toxicological data available and exposure data obtained from the reported use/analytical levels of TiO_2 (E 171) considered in this opinion would not be of concern.

Data required

- In order to enable the Panel to establish a health-based guidance value (ADI) for the food additive TiO₂ (E 171), additional testing could be performed.
- An extended 90-day study or a multigeneration or extended-one generation reproduction toxicity study according to the current OECD guidelines could be considered.
- Such studies should be performed with TiO₂ (E 171) complying with the EU specifications and additionally including a characterisation of the particle size distribution of the test material.
- However, in deciding on actual testing, considerations of animal welfare need to be balanced against the improvement in the toxicological database within a tiered testing approach.

Some food for thought

- Tier 1 requirements for a new additive
 - Absorption data
 - Extended 90 day toxicity test
 - *In vitro* genotoxicity
- Triggers for tier 2 testing
 - Absorption data – absorption is not negligible
 - Extended 90 day toxicity test – adverse effects in systemic or local tissues or additional screening endpoints
 - *In vitro* genotoxicity – positive or equivocal requires *in vivo* genotoxicity

So if titanium dioxide were a new additive

- Absorption of TiO_2 is negligible
- *In vitro* genotoxicity equivocal triggers tier 2 genotoxicity but negative *in vivo* so not considered genotoxic
- No extended 90 day study but based on long term toxicity data unlikely to have adverse effects at limit dose, limited data on extended parameters but from available data effects unlikely
- Testing would probably stop at tier 1

The new EFSA evaluation

- Asked to comment on 4 specific papers by end of June
 - In accordance with Article 29(1)(a) of Regulation (EC) No 178/2002, the European Commission requests the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to provide a scientific opinion in relation to four new studies on the potential toxicity of titanium dioxide used as a food additive (E 171). In particular, EFSA is requested to carry out a scientific evaluation of those studies and to indicate whether they would merit re-opening the existing opinion of EFSA related to the safety of titanium dioxide (E 171) as a food additive.
- Key question is do they alter the weight of evidence

Which 4 papers?

- Bettini S., Boutet-Robinet E., Cartier C., Coméra C., Gaultier E., Dupuy J., Naud N., Taché S., Grysan P., Reguer S., Thieriet N., Réfrégiers M., Thiaudière D., Cravedi J.-P., Carrière M., Audinot J.-N., Pierre F.H., Guzylack-Piriou L., Houdeau E. (2017). Food-grade TiO₂ impairs intestinal and systemic immune homeostasis, initiates preneoplastic lesions and promotes aberrant crypt development in the rat colon. *Sci Rep.* 2017, 7:40373.
- Guo Z., Martucci N., Moreno-Olivas F., Tako E., Mahler G., Titanium dioxide nanoparticle ingestion alters nutrient absorption in an in vitro model of the small intestine. *NanoImpact*, 5 : 70-82, janvier 2017
- Heringa MB, Geraets L, van Eijkeren JCH, Vandebriel RJ, de Jong W and Oomen AG, 2016. Risk assessment of titanium dioxide nanoparticles via oral exposure, including toxicokinetic considerations. *Nanotoxicology* Vol. 10, Iss. 10, 2016
- Proquin H., Rodríguez-Ibarra C., Moonen C., Urrutia Ortega I., Briedé J., de Kok T., van Loveren H., Chirino Y. , Titanium dioxide food additive (E171) induces ROS formation and genotoxicity: contribution of micro and nano-sized fractions. *Mutagenesis*, Volume 32, Issue 1, 1 January 2017, Pages 139–149 doi: 10.1093/mutage/gew051. Epub 2016 Oct 27.

***considered in the context of the conclusions of
the EFSA opinion of 2016.***

Conclusions on the Bettini et al.(2017)

- Based on the Bettini et al. study, and the negative results of the NCI (1979) carcinogenicity studies in mice and rats, new findings not sufficient to raise a concern on the potential initiation or promotion properties of TiO₂ (E 171) on colon carcinogenesis;
- Determination of biomarkers for putative preneoplastic lesions in the colon, as an additional parameter to be examined in the ongoing extended one generation reproductive toxicity study.
- Not enough justification for a new carcinogenicity study (large number of animals), but that if additional mechanistic studies provided useful information on the relevance of the reported results, this could be reconsidered in future;

Conclusions on the Proquin et al.(2017)

- Useful for hazard evaluation of TiO₂ nanoparticles (under the specific conditions of the study protocol). However, the relevance of the results for risk assessment of the food additive E 171 has not been established;
- Do not change the conclusion on the genotoxicity of TiO₂ as stated in the previous EFSA Opinion (2016) on the safety of TiO₂ (E171) when used as a food additive;
- One of the authors mentioned that consistent results appeared to be observed in mouse colon in ongoing in vivo transcriptomics studies. Therefore, the overall database might require reassessment when these studies are completed, if necessary, but that any such assessment should consider the entire literature available at that time.

Conclusions on the Guo et al.(2017)

- The results from the Guo et al. (2017) study cannot be extrapolated to the human situation and cannot be used for the risk assessment of the food additive TiO_2 (E171).

Conclusions on the Heringa et al.(2016)

- Significant uncertainty in the assessment carried;
- Not a weight of evidence analysis of the whole database on E171;
- This assessment consistent with a hazard from TiO₂ NP when dosed as in the selected studies, but the relevance to nanoparticles in a food matrix could not be assessed;
- The additional studies called for in its 2016 opinion should provide a more robust basis for addressing the reported effects in reproductive organs in the studies used by Heringa et al.(2016).

What did the EFSA ANS Panel conclude?

- The results of the Bettini et al. (2017) study did not provide enough justification for a new carcinogenicity study, but, should additional useful mechanistic information become available, this could be reconsidered in future;
- the new in vitro findings in the study by Proquin et al. (2017) did not modify the conclusion on the genotoxicity of TiO₂ as stated in the previous EFSA opinion (EFSA ANS Panel, 2016) on the safety of TiO₂ (E171) when used as a food additive;
- the effects of engineered TiO₂ nanoparticles reported by the Guo et al. (2017) study were of uncertain biological significance and therefore of limited relevance for the risk assessment of the food additive TiO₂ (E171);
- there was significant uncertainty in the risk assessment performed by Heringa et al. (2016), which did not include a weight of evidence analysis of the whole database;
- the four studies evaluated, highlighted some concerns but with uncertainties, therefore their relevance for the risk assessment was considered limited and further research would be needed to decrease the level of uncertainties.

What did the EFSA ANS Panel conclude?

- Overall, three of the studies assessed in this opinion reported that TiO₂ was able to induce various effects in in vitro and in vivo models. These studies may be useful for hazard identification of TiO₂. The Panel considered that the limited relevance of the protocols of these studies to the use of E 171 under realistic conditions in food, hampered the use of the data in the risk assessment of the food additive E 171.
- In the fourth study by Heringa et al. (2016), numerous assumptions were made, which resulted in large uncertainty in their conclusion.
- More research exploring the possible effects observed in three of the four studies could address their applicability to the risk assessment of the food additive E 171 under realistic conditions of use.
- Altogether, the Panel concluded that the outcome of the four studies *did not merit re-opening the existing opinion of EFSA related to the safety of titanium dioxide (E 171) as a food additive.*

What did the EFSA ANS Panel recommend?

- in order to substantiate the observations in the Bettini et al. (2017), biomarkers for putative preneoplastic lesions in the colon as additional parameters should be examined in the extended one generation reproductive toxicity study recommended by EFSA (EFSA ANS Panel, 2016);
- further studies on TiO_2 NP should include administration in a food matrix.

Titanium dioxide (E 171): update on EFSA's activities

Federica Lodi

Food Additives Team

Food Ingredients and Packaging Unit

Workshop on Possible adverse effects of
food additive E171 (titanium dioxide)

5-6 July 2018, Amsterdam

RE-EVALUATION MANDATE

Single mandate covering all food additives to be re-evaluated

Calls for data

RE-EVALUATION: DATA COLLECTION

All available data

- Published literature
- Previous evaluations
- Unpublished reports

TITANIUM DIOXIDE (E 171) TIMELINE

FOLLOW UP OF EFSA OPINION FROM EC

- Call for scientific and technical data:

https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_improvement_agents/additives/re-evaluation_en

- **Published:** 30/01/2017.
- **Registration of the contact details of business operators interested in submitting data (step 1)**
Deadline: 02/03/2017
- **Confirmation of data submission, deadlines and milestones (step2)**
Deadline: 30/07/2017)

FOLLOW UP OF EFSA OPINION FROM EC

- **Data on particle size and particle size distribution:** The Titanium Dioxide Manufacturers Association (TDMA) has committed to provide update specifications, including information on particle size and particle size distribution, for the food additive E 171. The data expected to be submitted by **30 June 2018**.
- **Toxicological data:** dietary Extended One-Generation Reproductive Toxicity Study with E171 food-grade titanium dioxide in rats (by The Titanium Dioxide Manufacturers Association, TDMA), including cohort 1 (extension by mating of F1 animals to the F2 generation), cohort 2 (for developmental neurotoxicity) and cohort 3 (for developmental immunotoxicity). **Deadline: August 2019**.

FOLLOW UP OF EFSA OPINION FROM EC

- Data on the lowest achievable limits for the impurities of toxic elements (arsenic, lead, mercury and cadmium) in titanium dioxide (E 171).
- Data on the actual use of alumina (aluminium oxide) in E171 formulations/lowest achievable limit for the use of alumina in those formulations.

COLLABORATION WITH ANSES (1Q 2017)

- **March 2017** → ANSES assessed the impact of the **Bettini et al. 2017** study
- **Collaboration with ANSES**
- **ANSES technical hearing** with the authors of the study
- **Joint meetings** between ANSES and EFSA experts
- **ANSES conclusion: no need to reopen the EFSA Opinion**

RECENT UPDATE FROM ANSES

- Working group dealing with nano in food but not specifically on titanium dioxide (E171).
- ANSES is the Member State to carry out the assessment of titanium dioxide in the Community Rolling Action Plan (**CoRAP**) under the REACH Regulation, and the deadline to complete this task is **March 2019**.

ECHA ACTIVITIES

- **2Q 2017:** TC meeting between ECHA and EFSA, updating on current activities.

- EFSA followed the discussion at the RAC.
- **ECHA conclusions (June 2017):**
 - Classification of titanium dioxide as a “substance suspected of causing cancer” (**category 2**) (**via inhalation**) Relevance to FEEDAP for occupational exposure

- **No concern** about carcinogenicity of titanium dioxide **via oral or dermal administration.**

RECENT MANDATE FROM THE EC (MARCH 2018)

- The European Commission sent a **mandate** to EFSA requesting the assessment of four studies published after the publication of the 2016 ANS Panel opinion, in accordance with Article 29 (1)(a) of the Regulation (EC) No 178/2002, and indicating whether these studies would merit to reopen the existing opinion.

EUROPEAN COMMISSION
DIRECTORATE-GENERAL FOR HEALTH AND FOOD SAFETY

Food and feed safety, innovation
Director

Brussels, 22 03 2018
SANTE.E2/AF/7km (2018) 1605112
Ares (2018) 1583962

Dear Dr Url,

Subject: Request for a scientific opinion from the European Food Safety Authority in relation to four new studies on the potential toxicity of titanium dioxide used as a food additive (E 171)

- Bettini et al., 2017
- Heringa et al., 2016
- Proquin et al., 2017
- Guo et al., 2017

PAFF COMMITTEE (APRIL 2018)

- Note from the French authorities sent to the EC on 15 February 2018 requesting interim protective measures (in accordance with Article 53 of the General Food Law) to address the uncertainties in respect of the impact on human health of titanium dioxide in food.
- Implementation of measures for suspension of the placing on the market or use of the food additive titanium dioxide (E171) in all food of European origin and measures for suspension of imports of all food containing that food additive from third countries.

PAFF COMMITTEE (APRIL 2018)

- France based this request on the fact that:
 - in the re-evaluation of the safety of titanium dioxide (E 171) as a food additive (Scientific Opinion published on 14 September 2016) EFSA was unable to reach a definitive conclusion on the reproductive and developmental toxicity endpoint and therefore EFSA did not establish an acceptable daily intake (ADI).
 - four studies on the potential toxicity of titanium dioxide used as a food additive (E 171), which were published after the adoption of EFSA's Opinion, pose some concern.

https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/safety/docs/reg-com_toxic_20180417_sum.pdf

RECENT MANDATE FROM THE EC (MARCH 2018)

- The WG on the Re-evaluation of Food Colours of the ANS Panel was preparing this scientific opinion for further discussion and adoption by the ANS Panel:
 - **15-17 May 2018:** first discussion at Plenary open to observers.
 - **Authors** of the studies attended as **hearing experts:** overview on their findings and answer to questions
- **Adoption by the ANS Panel: 26 June 2018**
- **Publication: 4th July 2018**

TITANIUM DIOXIDE AS A FEED ADDITIVE

- Assessment of titanium dioxide as feed additive **ongoing:** by EFSA FEEDAP Panel;
- Same EOGRTS study has been asked to their applicant: waiting for additional data.

NEXT STEPS

- The outcome of the **recently adopted opinion** (EFSA, June 2018) will be considered by **risk managers**.
- **EC to receive the following data:**
 - particle size and particle size distribution **by 30 June 2018**
 - EOGRTS reproductive toxicity study **by August 2019**.
- Other **ongoing evaluations:** EFSA FEEDAP Panel, ANSES/ECHA,

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